

CUSP NEWS

FAREWELL / FOREWORD

Ramping up for results

As Alba Hernández (PlasticHeal) passes the CUSP chair to Rudolf Reuther (PlasticsFatE), significant progress has been made in researching the risks of micro- and nanoplastics on human health. Notable achievements include organizing a workshop series on human risk assessment and launching the first CUSP Policy Brief. Ongoing initiatives on inter-lab comparisons, true-to-life materials, and human biomonitoring continue to advance knowledge in the field. Looking ahead, Rudolf Reuther, the new CUSP chair for 2023, envisions an intensified research phase, tackling challenges in methodology validation and development with real test materials and systems.

[Discover more about the plans for the year in progress in his introduction on page 2](#)

WORKING GROUPS & PROJECT UPDATES

Uniting global expertise

CUSP researchers have been busy advancing research across all six working groups. Read more about the upcoming interlaboratory comparison which promises to be the largest initiative of its kind hosted by the pre-standardisation platform VAMAS. Look inside our newsletter to learn more about this massive initiative, the progress in our working groups and the latest news from our five projects.

[Read more starting from page 4](#)

EVENTS AND ANNOUNCEMENTS

CUSP members will gather in Utrecht from Sep. 12th to 14th for the cluster's third annual meeting. During this event, they will review the achievements of the past year and plan future activities. Find out more about the meeting and a series of interesting conferences, all taking place in the months to come.

[Read more starting from page 17](#)

MEET OUR SCIENTISTS

... and discover the motivations that fuel their work as you delve into their inspiring stories.

This time we talked to Tatjana Parac-Vogt, a bio-inorganic scientist from KU Leuven and Runyu Zou from the University Medical Center Utrecht, an expert in the field of environmental epidemiology and exposome science.

[Discover more about their personal research journeys on page 21](#)

Farewell

Alba Hernández Bonilla

Autonomous University of Barcelona
2022 CUSP Chair

As my tenure as the chair of CUSP comes to an end, I am proud to reflect on the relevant work we have accomplished together.

Our research cluster has joined efforts to address methodological and knowledge gaps related to micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) exposure and effects with the aim to identify possible safety issues and risks for humans.

Through our collaborative work, we have achieved significant results in the areas of MNPs sampling and monitoring, MNPs human exposure and fate, MNPs-induced effects, and MNPs risk assessment and evaluation. At a more concrete level, part of the ongoing work within the CUSP Working Groups is focused on some of the following topics: an inter-lab comparisons initiative on MNPs size determination, obtention on MNPs true-to-life materials, human bio-monitoring and case studies, MNPs in vitro dosimetry, in silico modelling of MNPs fate and kinetics, FAIR data, human risk assessment (HRA) framework analysis, and the organization of an HRA workshop series, each session of which gathered over 150 participants from different fields and from around the world.

Our participation in different events organized inside and outside of CUSP, and the launch of the first

[Policy Brief](#), have helped increase the visibility of our research and its relevance for society. And we're not stopping there - the scientific and communication teams are working on new policy briefs, the next of which will focus on how the results achieved by the different CUSP projects respond to current EU regulatory initiatives tackling the impact of MNPs on human health.

I am particularly proud of the level of knowledge exchange that the five projects have established at the scientific and the communication level, and of the high number of opportunities we've taken to share our views, results and plans with stakeholders, policymakers, industry representatives, risk assessors, and scientists outside the cluster. Learning from their perspectives has certainly been an added value.

At the internal level, this year we have also established the 'early-stage researchers annual meeting' and promoted short-term exchanges of research staff to maximize the involvement of our younger members in the activities of the cluster, thus benefiting their career development

in the MNPs field, and facilitating the collaboration between labs.

As I step down from my position, I am confident that CUSP will continue to thrive under the leadership of our new coordinator. I wish them all the best and look forward to seeing the continued progress of our research consortia in the years to come.

The five CUSP projects

AURORA

IMP TOX

POLYRISK

PlasticsFatE

plasticheal

Rudolf Reuther

Environmental Assessments (ENAS)
2023 CUSP Chair

Foreword

A sincere 'thank you' to Tanja (Imptox) and Alba (PlasticHeal), for meticulously and successfully leading the CUSP cluster through its first two years.

Now, at the midterm point, the chair passes to PlasticsFatE to guide this unique research endeavour through its third year, when many new fundamental research results are being produced that shed light on existing questions regarding the impact of MNPs on human health. This year brings major challenges, and all five CUSP projects will join their research efforts across the six working groups, as well as the newly established sub-groups looking at human biomonitoring, and in vitro/in vivo, ex vivo, and in silico modelling of MNPs. Together we will address common questions,

and identify overlaps and synergies, expertise, and resources which can maximize our final impact and optimize our EU funding.

A major challenge lies in testing, validating and further adapting our developed methodologies, using increasingly more complex and real test materials and systems. These include aged, and weathered and leached plastics (e.g. from food packaging, textiles, and cosmetics), as well as identifying critical exposure levels and routes from food, drinking water, beverages, and indoor and outdoor air. Collectively, we are investigating different contexts that may present risks to specific demographics, including workers in plastics manufacturing and recycling plants, sportspeople using artificial turf, people living in coastal areas or close to dense traffic, and vulnerable groups such as children and pregnant women.

Another focus will be a closer analysis of the behaviour of NPs and additives as well as chemical/biological contaminants associated with MNPs that may affect human health and overcome the challenge of es-

tablishing and applying appropriate methodologies.

Each project is now embarking on an intense research phase, where our established approaches and models for measurement and testing will become increasingly exposed to more 'real' test materials. To this end, we will use 2D/3D cell lines and MNP specific biomarkers, and new computational fate/exposure and animal models. Ultimately, this will generate the solid scientific database required to reveal the impact of MNPs on human health and so guide policy, industry and regulation in the safe and sustainable handling, use, and disposal of plastic products.

I would therefore like to take this opportunity to warmly thank all CUSP partners for their strong commitment in this pioneering research initiative, and our early career researchers, who are doing a fantastic job of producing the high-quality scientific data we need to extend the existing frontiers of our limited knowledge on the behaviour of MNPs in the human body.

While collaborating on transversal themes in six common working groups, each one of the five CUSP research projects concentrates on specific aspects related to MNPs and health, from early life to adulthood.

To learn more, visit us on www.cusp-research.eu and follow us on social media.

PROGRESS ACROSS OUR CUSP WORKING GROUPS

Coordinating five research projects, each one a comprehensive research initiative in its own right, is an ambitious task. To collaborate most effectively across the five projects, ensuring that research processes

and support tasks are harmonised, we have divided our work into different working groups. Read on for recent working group updates and key takeaways from the last six months.

LEAD

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Data sharing

The role of data for MNP particle analysis and health outcome prediction.

The work under WG2 has focused on addressing how data collected in various CUSP projects need to become available for future use. Currently, all CUSP partners are in contact with IDEA to align data templates and matching standard operating procedures (SOPs) to allow for their use in data platforms such as eNanoMapper. When needed new data templates will be developed, for instance for physico-chemical analyses and for human biomonitoring studies.

Human biomonitoring data pose a particular ethical (GDPR) issue for which a solution is still under investigation. In addition, human biomonitoring studies involve real-world exposure

scenarios, that not only will provide human exposure and effect data but also real-world particles. These particles, for instance collected from traffic scenarios or the textile industry, are more complex and diverse than pristine micro- and nanoparticles used in most vitro studies. Since one of the outlooks of usage of CUSP data is to predict health outcomes based on particle characteristics, we need to further study physicochemical properties of these real world MNP. Real-world MNP data will be used to better define which properties link to human health effects. In the coming period, particles collected will be further characterized for types of polymers and adherent pollutants.

LEAD

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Exposure assessment

Collaboration to advance external and internal exposure assessment of micro- and nanoplastics.

Exposure assessment of micro/nanoplastics (MNPs) is complex given that MNPs are highly diverse in their properties and composition, and because methodological approaches are largely in the early stages of development. Working Group 4 has continued to exchange methodological advancements across projects with respect to sampling and measuring MNPs in internal and external settings. The five CUSP projects collectively are sampling external sources (drinking water, environmental water, outdoor air, indoor air, occupational settings, household dust, food, personal care products, etc.) and internal biological samples (urine, blood, feces, GI tract, placenta, etc.). A sub-working group on modelling of exposure and fate has been

established, led by the Spanish Council of Research (CSIC) of the CUSP partner-project PlasticsFatE. Led by Working Group 4 members at Sciensano, we have developed a framework for exposure assessment of MNPs considering methodological approaches for characterizing exposure and hazards, and also for regulatory needs. This framework builds upon the outcomes of the CUSP workshop and survey organized by Working Group 4 in 2022 on “Micro/nanoplastic exposure metrics: Priorities for research to inform human health risk assessment”. This work will be extended to develop a consensus statement on exposure metrics and exposure assessment approaches required for human health risk assessment of MNPs.

LEAD

 plasticheal

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Risk assessment

Generating scientific evidence on the hazards of micro-and nanoplastics for regulatory risk assessment purposes

From March to April, the dedicated efforts of CUSP WG5 were focused on the organisation and successful implementation of a series of workshops on human risk assessment of MNPs. A total of three workshops were held, each focusing on different aspects of risk assessment and knowledge gaps. The first workshop, led by PlasticHeal, focused on providing regulatory insights and identifying knowledge gaps. PolyRisk led the second workshop, which focused on risk assessment frameworks, and PlasticsFatE organised the third workshop, which focused on data and information gaps.

During these events, various stakeholders and CUSP researchers gave insightful presentations, sharing their research and perspectives on critical areas such as research needs, tools required for

risk assessment, and the types of data gaps that currently exist. More than 150 different stakeholders and scientists were present throughout the series, making it a very successful and well-attended event.

Feedback from the workshops was very encouraging, with many participants commenting positively on the quality of the information presented and the discussions held. CUSP WG5 is currently actively evaluating the outcome of the workshops and gathering feedback to guide future work in this area. The collective knowledge and outcomes of the workshops are expected to facilitate the development of a more robust human risk assessment framework that can better inform future policy making and risk management strategies.

LEAD

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Communication and dissemination

Maximising and sustaining the visibility and impact of the CUSP projects among target audiences in support of the European Plastics and Bioeconomy Strategies at European and international levels

WG6 work continues with regular news updates on the [CUSP website](#); updates to our [events listings](#); coordination of the [biannual newsletter](#); promotion of CUSP events; and raising awareness of [significant developments](#) related to our research.

We continue to reach out and forge relations with complementary initiatives, as well as consolidate existing ones and our recent liaisons with the PAPHILLONS Project led to the Project Coordinator, Luca Nizzetto, delivering a highly informative presentation at the recent 3rd Workshop and collaborating with us at the forthcoming large-scale CUSP Conference in Utrecht in September.

The past six months has seen WG6 form a close working relationship with WG5 to produce two key outcomes: the first of these is the first CUSP Policy Brief, which you can access [here](#). Production of the second Policy Brief, in which we will demonstrate with our findings how CUSP research addresses the policies listed in the first brief. At the same time, we have been supporting the promo-

tion of the series of three CUSP online workshops on Human Risk Assessment of MNPs. Each of these was co-organised by one of the CUSP projects, WG5 and WG6 and attracted over 250 registrants each time. The proceedings of the first workshop can be accessed [here](#). Proceedings from the last two workshops will be available very soon.

WG6 is also involved in the Scientific Organisation committees of two major events this summer: [The NanoSafety Training School](#), Venice, Italy from May 15th to 19th 2023; and [nanoSAFE and the NanoSafety Cluster conference](#), Grenoble, France from June 5th to 9th, 2023.

Finally, among the materials we're producing to raise awareness of the Cluster, we have produced a QR code (below) for easy access to our contact page where anyone can join our community. Please feel free to share this with any colleagues or contacts who may be interested in CUSP's work.

Inter-laboratory comparisons

Harmonizing the process for accurate and comparable results on micro- and nanoplastics identification and quantification methods in an international framework

We are proud to announce that the upcoming interlaboratory comparison (ILC) on microplastics has gathered 85 interested participants from over 20 countries, this being not only the first, but the ILC with the largest number of participants under the pre-standardisation platform of VAMAS (<http://www.vamas.org/twa45/>) so far. Such a large number of participants requires also significantly higher efforts in sample preparation (pressing, bottling, labeling etc.). More than 5000 pressed pellets of polymers embedded in a soluble matrix and blind values lacking the polymer have been produced. Each pellet has been placed separately in a glass bottle and blank samples (with no microplastics particles) have been prepared 6 in a bottle. Bottles have been labeled accordingly and have a unique ID number. Initially, the shipping of the samples has been announced to be in January/February 2023, however, we report a delay of several weeks due to the additional

effort necessary to deal with this very large number of participants (packaging, VAT number gathering, etc.). SOPs for sample preparation and for each measurement technique have been prepared. A dedicated xls-sheet for reporting of results has also been prepared and will be uploaded onto each ILC participant folder on the VAMAS sharepoint. The first shipping of the samples is just accomplished! Next samples will be shipped beginning next week in several steps due to the limited postal delivery capacities.

The homogeneity and stability tests are ongoing, and first results have already been obtained. The homogeneity control of samples (n=20 samples) for thermo-analytical methods has been performed by means of TED-GC/MS and for the vibrational spectroscopy by means of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) for particle counting and size distribution information (n=20).

We plan to complete the shipment process of all the samples by end of May 2023. The ILC participants have been given 4 weeks to carry out the measurements. It is planned to upload the xls-sheets filled with the results obtained by the end of June 2023. We wish good luck to all ILC participants!

LEAD

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Photo of the samples (only a half of samples) during the laborious packaging process at BAM. A shipping box contains: cover letter, SOPs, 6 samples for each polymer and 6 samples for blind values.

NEWS & UPDATES FROM CUSP & OUR PROJECTS

CUSP

CUSP workshop series on Human Risk Assessment of MNPs

The European UniThree online thematic workshops took place in the spring organised by the Working Group on Risk Assessment and partner projects

As part of CUSP's aim to investigate and discuss the applicability of existing risk assessment frameworks related to micro- and nanoplastics, the [CUSP Working Group on Risk Assessment](#), together with the CUSP member projects, organised a series of online thematic workshops in the Spring of 2023 under the theme "Human Risk Assessment of Micro- and Nanoplastics".

Around 150 professionals from different fields, collaborators of the five CUSP research projects, and representatives from various EU and international regulatory authorities gathered on February 7th for the [first workshop](#), organized by WG5 and PlasticHeal, and focused on the [regulatory insights and knowledge gaps](#) that may hinder scientific work. It was divided into three blocks: a first part dedicated to EU policy updates, the second to present scientific insights into risk assessment, and the final one to discuss the current and future work and challenges on this issue from the CUSP cluster's five projects. The video recording of the workshop, as well as the presentations, are available in the [Zenodo document repository](#) and to [stream on YouTube](#).

The [second workshop](#) within the series was about risk assessment frameworks on March 14th and was organized by WG5 and PolyRisk. Over 145 participants gathered online including experts like Oliver Peters (BAuA) who outlined the risk assessment of polymers in the perspective of EU's flagship chemicals legislation, REACH. Steffen Foss Hansen (DTU) introduced the risk assessment of nanomaterials. Later, Annie Jarabek (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency) talked about integrated approaches for testing and assessment for poorly soluble, low toxicity polymer particles. Matthew Boyles (Institute of Occupational Medicine - IOM) covered whether existing frameworks for nanomaterials are useful for MNPs.

Andrea Haase (German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment - BfR) outlined POLYRISK's draft risk assessment framework for MNPs. The workshop concluded with an engaging break-out session, where participants tackled questions around setting priorities for future research.

The third workshop, organized by WG5 and PlasticsFatE, took place on April 21st and focused on data and information gaps. The event, titled "Practice-based analysis of data needs, availability, reuse and gaps for MNP-risk related tools" comprised two sessions. In the first: "Types of data needed for tools related to risk of MNP in CUSP and beyond," presenters from four CUSP projects and the PAILLONS initiative provided input, followed by a preliminary summary on data needs from Christina Hipfinger (BOKU), and a structured discussion about key requirements in terms of data. In the second session, which focused on data sources and data processing for risk related tools, Anita Jemec Kokalj (University of Ljubljana) presented a quality assessment approach, which was followed by an introduction to data sources/eNanoMapper, types and definitions of data by Nina Jeliakova, IDEAconsult Ltd. The event attracted over 135 professionals from various backgrounds, as shown in the mentimeter slide above.

The proceedings of all three workshops will soon be available on the [CUSP Zenodo community](#).

AURORA

Of methods and models: Focus on detecting nanoplastics and on studying MNP impacts in the placenta

Two recent AURORA publications review available analytical methods to analyze nanoplastics in human bio samples as well as in vitro and ex vivo placenta models; the research provides a fundamental basis for the next phase of experiments.

For researching MNPs impacts on early life health, appropriate analytical methods and representative toxicological models are required. Recently, AURORA researchers have been busy assessing the state of the science for both topics, and they have published two review publications.

The accurate detection and characterization of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) in human biosamples is essential for human exposure assessment. Ideally, both particle numbers, as well as the chemical compositions of MNPs, would be analysed using methods that have low detection limits. But especially for nanoplastics (NPs) their analysis is very challenging for several reasons: firstly, because they are too small they cannot be imaged by light-based microscopes (e.g., using ultraviolet, visible, or infrared wavelengths), and secondly, because of the particle-to-mass ratio where the particle number may be high, but the actual mass is still very low – meaning that mass-based analytical methods need to have extremely low detection and quantification limits for successful application. What is more, the elemental composition of NPs (mainly carbon, oxygen, and hydrogen) is very similar to the elements that are abundant in human bio samples, which further complicates the analysis when methods are used that rely on contrasts between chemical elements. AURORA researchers Laurens Mandemaker and Florian Meirer, both at Utrecht University, have now

described the available methods for NP analysis in bio samples in a recently [published review](#) in the journal *Angewandte Chemie*. They also discuss the main challenges and describe future research needs. [Read more](#) on the AURORA website.

To study the impacts of MNPs on fetal development, AURORA researchers have also [recently reviewed](#) the uptake, transport, and toxicity of MNPs in the human placenta and compiled an overview of available in vitro and ex vivo models. Lead author of the new study Hanna Dusza, University of Utrecht, highlights that important knowledge gaps exist when it comes to studying impacts of MNPs on placental functioning. And co-lead author Jeske van Boxel, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, specifies that such a technical overview is necessary for carrying out targeted studies. Importantly, most experimental data are from acute, high-dose exposures with manufactured polystyrene MNPs, while more realistic exposures (in terms of MNP types and concentrations) have not yet commonly been studied. [Read more](#) on the AURORA website.

As the AURORA consortium moves into its third year, its partners are preparing for their second in-person project meeting, which will be held mid-May in Switzerland. Looking ahead, four hundred placental samples have now been shipped for analysis at consortium partner Doug Walker's new lab at Emory University in Atlanta, Georgia, USA, and we look forward to these data that will enable a better understanding of MNP levels in placentas from our cohort.

Image Credit: Mandemaker and Meirer, 2023

IMPTOX

Experts gather at Imptox workshop to discuss the emerging understanding of micro- and nanoplastics' impact on human health

On Friday, March 24th, 2023, the successful Imptox public workshop attracted a numerous audience discussing the potential health impacts of micro- and nanoplastics with experts from all over Europe.

The hybrid workshop took place at the Pyramide Event Hotel in Vienna with 91 participants registered online and dozens taking part in person. The workshop included six speakers from across Europe, each offering a unique perspective on the topic ([click here](#) for the detailed agenda).

Ian Mudway discussed the impact of plastic particles as a component of PM2.5 air pollution. He emphasized that “we do not breathe microplastics alone”, but rather inhale them in the context of a complicated biological and inorganic cloud of materials. To understand their impact on human health, it is fundamental to grasp how they fall into the general landscape of toxins and toxicants.

Hans-Peter Grossart presented about the release of microplastics into freshwater via waste-water treatment plants. Theo Vermeire spoke about the difficulty of assessing the risk of micro- and nanoplastics for human health, and Thomas Meisel urged the research community to focus on nanoplastics rather than microplastics due to their greater ecological and health impact.

Verena Pichler and Lukas Kenner discussed their involvement in the MicroOne project, which investigates the health effects of micro- and nanoplastics. Kenner presented animal in vivo data showing that only two hours

after oral MNP intake, plastic particles were found in the brain and after ten days, they were found in the blood and in most organs while chronic intestinal inflammation and macrophages in intestinal tissue had increased.

The Imptox public workshop was the crowning end of two days of internal meetings of the Imptox consortium in which they reviewed their research progress and made plans for the coming year.

Thanks to the thought-provoking questions and discussions involving presenters and participants, the workshop provided everyone with a valuable opportunity for knowledge exchange and reflection.

Discover Imptox shorts featuring junior researchers!

[Check out](#) the first series of Imptox short video clips and find out what motivated its early-career scientists to pursue science, while gaining insight into their specific research tasks. Learn about their daily challenges and much more straight from their own perspectives.

Lukas, a Ph.D. student in the pharmaceutical technology and biopharmaceutics department at the University of Vienna, initially wanted to become a graphics designer. However, he soon realized that creativity was just as important in science, especially when it came to developing innovative solutions to complex problems. Similarly, Mohamed, a postdoctoral researcher at Ghent University, believes that science provides a limitless source to think about the world without borders.

In this series of Imptox Shorts, we have interviewed five

junior researchers, each with their unique story: **Sandra, Nikola, Tamara, Lukas, and Mohamed**. Despite their diverse backgrounds and research interests, they share a strong passion for science and discovery.

Ph.D. students and postdocs play a crucial role in Imptox, leading the way in various research tasks and carrying out the daily work in labs and libraries. By watching their videos, you'll get the chance to delve deeper into their personal and professional lives and learn more about what drives them to pursue scientific research.

POLYRISK

Launch of POLYRISK Flyer

Polyrisk just launched a flyer that highlights the project's objectives, how it examines human exposure, including occupational exposure to nano- and microplastics, to better understand their potential adverse effects on the immune system, and links to CUSP. Throughout the project, researchers are examining external and internal exposure to microplastics in humans in five real-life scenarios:

- Exposure to traffic-related pollution
- Exposure to MNPs from soccer fields with artificial turf with rubber granulate infill
- Occupational exposure in the rubber tire refurbishing industry
- Exposure to MNPs from bottled drinking water ingestion
- Occupational exposure in the textile industry

The flyer provides a brief overview of the project and is aimed at a wide audience.

Discussions on MNP research at SETAC Europe 2023

POLYRISK project partners from Fraunhofer, BAM, and the National Research and Development Institute for Textiles and Leather attended the annual meeting of the Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC) held in late April focused on the addressing the theme of “Data-driven environmental decision-making” for the protection and restoration of the environment. There they presented two abstract posters on 1) Filtra-

tion tools for MNP number and mass-based analysis and 2) Real-life airborne MNP particles and fibres on a porous membrane filter system from a textile factory suitable for both: vibrational and mass spectrometry.

PLASTICSFATE

PlasticsFatE advances research on micro- and nanoplastics: Latest updates

From test materials to hazard assessment, PlasticsFatE makes strides in understanding the impact of MNPs on human health.

PlasticsFatE, has made significant progress throughout the last months. They have developed a diverse portfolio of test materials consisting of different types of polymers with varying sizes and shapes, including aged and labelled particles. Protocols have been established to prepare stable suspensions for analysing the physicochemical and hazard characteristics of MNPs in biologically relevant test media.

To validate the methods for detecting and characterizing MNPs, PlasticsFatE has initiated two interlaboratory comparison studies in collaboration with CUSP and VAMAS. These studies aim to assess spectroscopic, thermo-analytic, microscopic, and other size-related methods for detecting and characterizing MPs and NPs. The first results from the ongoing interlaboratory comparison are expected in the second half of 2023.

PlasticsFatE plans to focus on test materials that have shown potential effects during their first testing and measurement period and on those obtained from weathering, aging, and leaching processes. They will also assess particles with an eco-corona and new industrial materials with and without additives or contaminants. Special attention will be given to micro-fibres derived from various sources to evaluate exposure levels for consumers and workers.

PlasticsFatE has developed new standard operating procedures for analysing MNPs in food and drinking water and first results have been achieved for bottled water, as well as indoor and outdoor air collected at two different lo-

cations (remote and suburban) (Figure 1). They are testing the applicability of fast-screening methods like MuScan for MNP analysis in food (Figure 2). PlasticsFatE is also investigating the occurrence of MNPs in human tissues and assessing the physicochemical changes and translocation of particles in the oral-gastro-intestinal tract using simulated digestion systems.

Regarding hazard assessment, initial studies have been conducted on different-sized particles and their effects on cell viability, barrier integrity, cellular uptake, bioaccumulation, and immunological response. While no significant effects have been observed after acute exposure to selected MNPs on cell viability and membrane integrity, certain particles have shown a small induction of inflammatory response. Long-term studies, the role of additives and contaminants, and the investigation of weathered particles and particles with an eco-corona are part of the next steps.

PlasticsFatE has launched case studies to assess the performance of their methodology in real conditions. These studies include monitoring occupational exposure and air collection at various locations, supported by human biomonitoring and clinical studies to evaluate long-term effects.

Lastly, PlasticsFatE is examining the role of MNPs in biofilm formation and pathogen transmission. Preliminary results indicate that MPs released from tire wear can promote horizontal gene transfer and contribute to biofilm generation.

plasticheal

PLASTICHEAL

Breakthrough advances presented at the PlasticHeal annual meeting

Researchers from the 11 partner institutions met in March to discuss the research progress and plan the actions for the months to come.

The PlasticHeal team celebrated its second general assembly on March 8-9th at the Wageningen University and Research (WUR), in the Netherlands. The leaders of the work packages explained the milestones achieved in providing data, methodologies, experimental models, and biological endpoints of effect for micro- and nano-plastics human risk assessment.

Up until now, a series of studies have been developed to analyse the **external human exposure to MNPs**. The partners have validated the **sampling strategies**, the **analytical workflow** and the **quality assurance protocols** for the **determination and characterisation of MNPs in food, environmental samples, tissues and biofluids**. The main next steps will be to apply these to the different sets of samples already available, and to the human samples that will be collected in the upcoming biomonitoring campaigns.

The consortium has generated a **catalogue of fully characterized true-to-life MNPLs materials**, including some at the nano scale, with the corresponding labelled counterpart necessary for toxicokinetic studies. More work is currently being done both inside the consortium and in collaboration with partners from CUSP to generate new types of true-to-life nano- MNPs materials.

Additionally, **PS beads have been extensively tested with the different experimental models developed** by the team, generating a big amount of data on genotoxicity, oxidative response, secretome alterations, inflammation, immune-related effects, carcinogenesis, and stemness imbalance with this material. Most of the results of

this research have already been published and are available on the PlasticHeal website.

True-to-life nano PET and nano PLA have also been well studied to screen for effects in the blood system, transcriptomic dysregulation, and carcinogenic effects. The work with these more realistic materials is ongoing.

The **gastrointestinal and respiratory models** have received special attention as the project understand those as the MNPLs primary barriers, and the compartments where more likely the MNPs will suffer from surface modifications with toxicological significance (e.g., by digestion). Noteworthy, the consortium has successfully established **ALI models and lung organoids**.

Regarding risk assessment, the consortium has developed a **public, on-line searchable database as a hub for MNPs risk assessment and regulatory relevant research**. Also, key risk assessment and regulatory issues/questions have been identified, and investigations on the applicability of existing risk assessment frameworks on nanomaterials are ongoing.

EVENTS AND ANNOUNCEMENTS

CUSP - Annual Meeting

CUSP 2023 Meeting in Utrecht (NL): Into our third year progressing together on research into the impact of micro- and nanoplastics on human health

Following on from the highly successful annual meeting held at JRC in Ispra last year, the third CUSP annual meeting will take place in [Jaarbeurs MeetUp](#), Utrecht, the Netherlands, on **Tuesday 12th and Wednesday 13th September 2023**.

Around 150 representatives from the five projects, representing a wide range of disciplines, will convene to share the latest research results and to discuss ongoing multidisciplinary collaboration through the working groups and sub-groups. It will also give the projects a common platform on which to discuss the progress made so far and the challenges faced in the forthcoming year. We will also hear about the latest policy developments and information needs from the European Commission.

This will be followed by a conference on **Thursday 14th September** which will include a number of

invited speakers. This will be a fantastic opportunity to share results from CUSP and discuss these with other like-minded initiatives. Together we will identify opportunities for collaboration and knowledge sharing that will help address remaining knowledge gaps on the impacts of MNP on human health. Conference outcomes will be shared with the wider community.

Save
the date

12 - 14

09

23

Stay tuned!

Join our Community,
follow us on [Twitter](#) and
[LinkedIn](#).

ANNOUNCEMENT

Nanosafety Training School 2023

CUSP and its partner projects are among the contributors of the Nanosafety Training School 2023, “SSbD Approaches for Chemicals, Advanced Materials and Plastics”. This is a unique opportunity to learn about nanosafety in the historic centre of Venice, Italy, from 14–19 May 2023.

This year’s sessions will be around the following topics:

- Safe-and-sustainable-by-design approaches for nanomaterials and advanced materials
- Environmental and health impacts of micro and nano plastics
- Physicochemical characterisation methods for advanced materials
- Methods to assess the release of advanced materials, their fate, biodistribution and exposure
- New approach methodologies (NAMs) for hazard assessment of advanced materials
- FAIR data management in nanoinformatics
- Computational modelling of properties and interactions
- Sustainability assessment methods (environmental, social and economic)
- How to make my method ready for regulatory acceptance?
- Policy perspectives on risk governance of nanotechnologies
- Science diplomacy: The role of interdisciplinarity in SSbD

Additionally, there will be several possibilities to network with the experts and other participants.

The school is organised by various EU-funded research

projects and other initiatives led by the H2020 project SUNSHINE. It offers hands-on sessions to learn State-of-the-Art knowledge from key experts in the field.

Venue: Venice, Italy, Auditorium Santa Margherita
Dates: 15–19 May 2023

Organisers:

- [DIAGONAL](#), [HARMLESS](#), [SUNSHINE](#)
- [ASINA](#), [SABYDOMA](#), [SAByNA](#), [SbD4Nano](#)
- [INFRAMES](#) initiative

ANNOUNCEMENT

2023 meetings of the European and the Spanish Mutagenesis and Genomics societies

The 51st congress of the [European Environmental Mutagenesis and Genomics Society \(EEMGS\)](#) will take place with [the 27th Scientific Meeting of the Spanish Environmental Mutagenesis and Genomics Society \(SEMA\)](#). The congress will be entitled “Back to the sunny seashore of genotoxicology: a dive into new developments and applications” and will be held in Málaga (Spain) from May 15th to 18th, 2023.

The scientific programme aims at including recent findings and current advances in mutagenesis and environmental genomics with a special dedication to applied and regulatory genotoxicity testing.

The main topics of the congress sessions include (but are not limited to):

- International workshop on genotoxicity testing (IWGT) session
- International Comet Assay Working Group (ICAWG) session
- Ecotoxicology
- Human biomonitoring
- DNA repair, Chromatin structure and Genome stability
- Error-corrected next-generation sequencing (ecNGS)
- Machine learning
- New challenges in genotoxicity assessment
- New Approach Methodologies
- Risk assessment
- Advances in regulatory genotoxicology

The EEMGS/SEMA 2023 congress will be accompanied by a satellite workshop organised by HESI and focused on “Quantitative Interpretation of Genetic Toxicity Dose-response Data for Risk Assessment and Reg Decision-making”, that will take place on May 15th, just before the beginning of the congress.

The workshop will provide an overview of recent developments in quantitative interpretation of genetic toxicity dose-response data; first by outlining basic concepts and best practices for PoD (point of departure) determination, then by outlining approaches to extrapolate below the PoD for risk assessment and regulatory decision-making. The latter half of the workshop will provide examples of applications related to impurities in pharmaceutical products. More specifically, examples that demonstrate how an approach based on quantitative dose-response analyses can be used to determine human exposure limits to potent genotoxicants.

ANNOUNCEMENT

CUSP at the WHO's Seventh Ministerial Conference on Environment and Health

A designated speaker will describe on behalf of the Cluster how the research developed by the partner projects is linked to policies and relevant actions tackling micro- and nanoplastics impacts on human health.

CUSP has been invited to participate in the parallel session organised by the [European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation](#) (DG RTD) during the [Seventh Ministerial Conference on Environment and Health](#) convened by the [World Health Organisation](#) (WHO) and to be held in Budapest **from July 5th - 7th**.

The main event is aimed at defining “the future environment and health priorities and commitments for the WHO European Region, with a focus on addressing the health dimensions of the triple environmental crisis of climate change, biodiversity loss and environmental pollution”, as described by the WHO on their website..

The aim of the parallel session organised by the DG RTD is to highlight the role of the European Union's (EU) funded research in **understanding the impact of different sources of environmental pollution** (e.g., indoor air quality, exposure to plastics, light in urban environments) **on human health**.

The poster for the 8th International Conference on Environmental, Health and Safety issues related to nanomaterials, titled 'nanoSAFE & NanoSafety Cluster 23'. It features a hexagonal graphic with the text '8th international conference on Environmental, Health and Safety issues related to nanomaterials' and 'Safe and Sustainable by Design advanced materials, products and processes'. The dates 'JUNE 5-9 2023' are prominently displayed. The website 'www.nanosafe.org' is provided, along with social media links for LinkedIn and CEA Liten. The location is 'Maison Minattec Grenoble, France'. Sponsors include the European Union, CEA, MINATEC, QSAR, and LUNATA. The text 'In partnership with' is also present.

ANNOUNCEMENT

NanoSAFE and the NanoSafety Cluster Conference

CUSP is playing a key role at the forthcoming nanoSAFE event, taking place in Grenoble, France, **from June 5th - 9th**, where Mark Morrison and Lesley Tobin (PlasticsFatE) will be chairing a half-day session titled ‘Micro and nanoplastics pollution.’

This session will give an overview on the state of the art, and gather insights and novel results on micro and nanoplastic pollutants (MNP) and their characterization. The session also aims to highlight the current and upcoming initiatives aiming at transferring the research knowledge into policies and regulations.

Organized every two years in Grenoble since 2008, the nanoSAFE conference shares the latest research results on health and safety issues related to nanomaterials and beyond for a socially responsible approach.

The 8th International Conference on Health and Safety Issues for a socially responsible approach to nanomaterials will enable CUSP to forge stronger links with the nanosafety community.

For more information about the event and to register, visit the nanoSAFE website

CUSP COLLABORATIONS

CUSP continues to collaborate with complementary initiatives, creating synergies and multiplying our joint efforts.

PAPILLONS stands for 'Plastic in Agricultural Production: Impacts, Life-cycle, and LONG-term Sustainability. In comparison with the CUSP projects, it has a slightly different focus and topic.

Plastics are becoming increasingly important in European agricultural production. Nonetheless, the long-term impacts of plastics in this area are still mostly unknown. PAPILLONS is a research project set up to investigate the impacts of micro and nanoplastics (MNP) in agricultural soils. The goal is to study the sources, behavior, and ecological effects of micro- and nanoplastics in agricultural soils, resulting from the use of agricultural plastics.

In doing so, PAPILLONS conducts a pan-European large field-scale experiment alongside sampling studies and laboratory tests. Furthermore, it has also established soil mesocosm experiments investigating MNP fate and

transport. PAPILLONS has equally managed to create batches of custom-designed reference materials of micro & nanoplastics. These can be used for reliable testing, assessment, and other research purposes.

The PAPILLONS Consortium has 20 partners from 12 countries, and is supported by the European Commission within the EU Horizon 2020 program. The Consortium represents cutting-edge research into agricultural plastic use and its impacts in Europe. It includes a network of world-leading experts from soil scientists to ecotoxicologists.

The PAPILLONS Consortium plans to deepen the existing relations with the CUSP projects by identifying cross-cutting areas, and other clustering activities. By working together we can cover a wider-reaching part of the food chain, and better understand the nature of plastics in our ecosystems.

Wish to collaborate?

If you are part of a project or organisation and would like to collaborate, please get in touch at hello@cusp-research.eu and register to join our community at <https://cusp-research.eu/contact/>

MEET OUR SCIENTISTS

... and discover the faces behind the CUSP projects! Find out what got them into science, what challenges they face in their scientific work and what drives them in their discovery of the impact of micro- and nanoplastics on human health.

Dr. Runyu Zou

Environmental epidemiology and exposome science
University Medical Center Utrecht

Project: **AURORA**

When asked about my dream job in kindergarten, my answer often switched between becoming a doctor or a scientist, even without understanding exactly what scientists really do. Looking back now, perhaps I should be proud that today I have the luxury to combine both roles by acting as a health scientist, specialized in epidemiology.

After finishing my medical and public health training, I pursued a PhD at Erasmus MC, investigating perinatal determinants on child brain development embedded in the Generation R cohort. I have been working within the AURORA project as an Assistant Professor since November 2021 focusing on developing human studies and integrating these results into risk assessments. I really appreciate the opportunity to be involved within CUSP as I have always been interested in the interaction between the environment and human health, and micro- and nanoplastics have increasingly become a research hotspot due to their widespread global distribution while little is known about the metabolism in the human body and potential health risks. The interdisciplinary nature of the AURORA project is also very appealing as someone who grew up with both parents working in the field of chemistry.

Prof. Tatjana Parac-Vogt

Chemistry
KU Leuven

Project: **IMPTOX**

As a bioinorganic chemist, my interest in the role of metals in biological systems began early on. I find it fascinating that metals are essential for life, yet they can also have detrimental effects on living organisms. This is what my group aims to investigate within the Imptox project - how the adsorption of toxic metals on microplastics impacts health.

When I was about 12 years old, I knew I wanted to pursue a PhD in science, thanks to a friend whose mother was a scientist. Still today I remember how I thought back then what a cool job that must be ! However, it wasn't until I had an inspiring female teacher in high school that I truly fell in love with chemistry. This taught me the importance of role models for young girls.

What I find most fascinating about my work is the ability to combine technical skill with creativity. Being a good scientist requires both, and I believe this is what makes my work so fulfilling.

While I don't measure my achievements in awards or publications, I see myself as someone who is constantly trying to empower and inspire younger researchers. My greatest achievement is when I see them succeed.

I live by the mantra that there are no failures, only lessons. Reliability is my favorite virtue in people, and I've been blessed to work with fantastic individuals. However, one of the biggest challenges in my research has been securing financial support for my team. That's the less fun part of my job.

In this new research project, I'm looking forward to working with an incredible group of multidisciplinary scientists. It's rare to have such an opportunity, and I'm excited to see what we can achieve together.

In the next 10 years, I hope that chemistry will play a key role in solving some of the world's environmental issues. Chemical pollution can have a profound impact on the Earth's ecosystems, but I'm optimistic that chemistry will also be instrumental in developing technological solutions for these problems.

Stay tuned!

Interested in our research journey on MNPS? Feel free to visit our [website](#)! Subscribe to our [newsletter](#) and follow us on [Twitter](#), and [LinkedIn](#) to get the latest news on our cluster!

The European research cluster to understand the health impacts of micro- and nanoplastics

The CUSP consortium: 75 organizations from 21 countries

AURORA: Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg | Food Packaging Forum Foundation | Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai | Instituto de Salud Global Barcelona (IS Global) | University of Eastern Finland | Masaryk University | University Medical Center Utrecht | Universiteit Hasselt | Universiteit Utrecht | Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam | Institute of Occupational Medicine (IOM)

IMPTOX: Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique CNRS | Haute Ecole Spécialisée de Suisse Occidentale | Karolinska Institutet | Katholieke Universiteit Leuven | Medizinische Universität Wien | Moverim consulting sprl | Promoscience srl | Sciensano | Srebrnjak children's hospital | Universität Wien | Universiteit Gent

PLASTICHEAL: Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona | Tyoterveyslaitos | Wageningen University | Danmarks Tekniske Universitet | Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives | Fundación para la Formación e Investigación Sanitarias de la Región de Murcia | The University of Manchester | Asociación de Investigación de Materiales Plásticos y Conexas | L'Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale | Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH | Universität Leipzig

PLASTICSFATE: ENAS | Optimat | European Research Services GmbH | Statens Arbejds miljøinstitut | Det Nationale Forskningscenter Forarbejds miljø | Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg | Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht | Stichting Wageningen Research | Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung | Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas | Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche | Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Angewandten Forschung e.v. | Helmholtz-zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH | Forschungsverbund Berlin eV | Universiteit Leiden | Univerza v Ljubljani | Universität für Bodenkultur Wien | Universität Bayreuth | Università degli Studi di Torino | Università degli studi di Roma Tor Vergata | Université de Paris | National Technical University of Athens | Instituto Tecnológico del Embalaje, Transporte y Logística | Ecamricert srl | Fundación Gaiker | Innosieve Diagnostics bv | Dechema Gesellschaft für Chemische Technik und Biotechnologie e.v. | Umweltbundesamt

POLYRISK: Utrecht University | Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam | Stichting VUmc | German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment | Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung | Bundesanstalt für Arbeitsschutz und Arbeitsmedizin | Norwegian Institute of Public Health | University Medical Centre Utrecht | The Research Development National Institute for Textile and Leather | Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development | Ideacon Ltd. | Health and Environment Alliance | Fraunhofer-Center für Silizium-Photovoltaik | European Research Services | Umweltbundesamt

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